

Ricefield weeds in South Andarnan, India

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We surveyed weeds in 103 randomly selected ricefields in 14 locations of South Andaman during Oct 1986. Percentage cover for all weed species was assessed in 51 clay loam soil and 52 clay soil fields between heading and

flowering.

Forty weed species belonging to 13 families were identified: 30% were Cyperaceae and 27.5% Poaceae (see table). Thirty-nine species were found in clay loam fields, 38 in clay fields; 37 were common to both conditions. *Eleocharis dulcis* was not found in clay loam fields; *Ageratum conyzoides*, and *Spilanthes paniculata* were not found in clay fields.

Fimbristylis miliacea was predominant in all the clay loam and

94% of the clay fields surveyed. *Echinochloa colona*, *Ludwigia hyssopifolia*, *Torenia violacea*, and *Cyperus rotundus* were almost equally important in both soil types.

Scirpus juncooides and *Monochoria vaginalis* in clay fields and *Cyperus difformis* in clay loam fields were also important. □

Percentage of fields infested with weeds and severity of infestation in transplanted upland and lowland rice in South Andaman.

Weed species	Family	Clay loam ^a		Clay soil ^b	
		Field infested (%)	Cover (%)	Field infested (%)	Cover (%)
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	100	27.6	94	23.0
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	84	7.4	75	1.8
<i>Ludwigia hyssopifolia</i> (G. Don) Exell	Onagraceae	80	2.1	71	2.5
<i>Torenia violacea</i> (Azaola ex Blanco) Pennell	Scrophulariaceae	64	2.7	75	6.3
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	64	8.2	63	5.0
<i>Scirpus juncooides</i> Roxb.	Cyperaceae	64	2.3	79	21.2
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm.f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	80	2.3	69	4.6
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	84	4.9	53	2.9
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	56	1.6	51	4.1
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	53	2.3	51	1.6
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv.	Poaceae	53	2.1	51	1.6
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	55	1.6	55	1.5
<i>Cryptocoryne ciliata</i> (Roxb.) Schott	Araceae	53	9.1	53	7.7
<i>Setaria verticillata</i> (L.) Beauv.	Poaceae	53	1.3	34	0.5
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	39	4.5	50	2.3
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Poaceae	29	2.4	34	1.1
<i>Fuirena umbellata</i> Rottb.	Cyperaceae	37	2.5	52	2.2
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schum & Thonn.	Euphorbiaceae	35	0.2	29	0.1
<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Pennell	Scrophulariaceae	33	1.3	38	1.2
<i>Cyperus javanicus</i> Houtt.	Cyperaceae	31	0.5	29	0.2
<i>Axonopus compressus</i> (Sw.) P. Beauv.	Poaceae	31	0.6	29	0.3
<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	29	0.5	29	0.3
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Asteraceae	29	0.3	—	—
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	29	1.9	23	1.5
<i>Eleocharis dulcis</i> (Burm. f.) Henschel	Cyperaceae	—	—	29	0.2
<i>Fimbristylis albiviridis</i> C. B. Clarke	Cyperaceae	23	0.1	23	0.1
<i>Aponogeton natans</i> (L.) Eng & Kr.	Aponogetonaceae	23	0.3	23	0.2
<i>Hedyotis umbellata</i> (L.) Lam.	Rubiaceae	27	0.3	6	0.1
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	Marsileaceae	23	0.4	23	0.7
<i>Spilanthes paniculata</i> Wall. ex DC.	Asteraceae	27	0.3	—	—
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	Poaceae	12	0.3	4	>1
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Poaceae	10	0.1	12	0.1
<i>Ischaerum indicum</i> (Houtt.) Merr.	Poaceae	2	0.6	12	0.1
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	8	1.9	6	>1
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	4	0.5	12	0.1
<i>Cyperus kyllinga</i> Endl.	Cyperaceae	2	0.3	8	0.1
<i>Murdannia nudiflora</i> (L.) Brenan	Commelinaceae	2	3.4	6	>1
<i>Cyperus halpan</i> L.	Cyperaceae	4	1.1	4	>1
<i>Cyperus sanguinolentus</i> Vahl	Cyperaceae	2	0.3	4	>1
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Commelinaceae	4	0.4	2	>1

^aDrained soils located on the lower edge of hills. During rainy season, these soils remain wet. ^bClay soils of valley areas. Water stagnates up to 15-20 cm during the rainy season. With short dry spells, the soils become dry. Rice transplanting is common in both clay loam and clay soils in Andaman, Nicobar Islands.

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Response of upland rice to weed control methods

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We evaluated 14 treatments to manage the complex weed ecosystem in upland rice. Each treatment was replicated four times in a randomized block design. Pusa 33 seed at 100 kg/ha was drilled in 20-cm-wide rows the first week of Jul. Fertilizer was 100-26-33 kg NPK/ha. All P and K and 1/2 N were applied at sowing; the remaining N was applied in 2 equal splits at 20 and 40 d after sowing (DAS).

Cyperus iria, *C. rotundus*, *Commelina diffusa*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Paspalum distichum*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Eclipta prostrata*, and *Alternanthera sessilis* were the major weeds in the experimental field. The weed biomass was determined at harvest.

Weed biomass was lowest with oxadiazon 0.75 kg ai/ha plus 1 hand weeding at 30 DAS (see table).

Effective tillers were highest with oxadiazon 0.75 kg ai/ha + 1 hand weeding at 30 DAS. Crop biomass was highest (13.7 t/ha) with thiobencarb 1.5 kg ai/ha + 1 hand weeding 30 DAS.

Highest grain (4.39 t/ha) and straw (9.29 t/ha) yields were observed with thiobencarb 1.5 kg ai/ha + 1 hand weeding at 30 DAS. The same treatment gave the highest profit (\$241.46/ha).

Influence of various weed control treatments on weed control efficiency, growth, and yield of upland rice. Jabalpur, India.

Treatment ^a	Weed biomass (t/ha)	Effective tillers/plant	Crop biomass (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Treatment cost ^b (\$/ha)	Profit ^c (\$)
Thiobencarb 1.5 + 1 HW 30 DAS	0.2	2.7	13.7	9.3	4.4	93.45	241.46
Oxadiazon 0.75 + 1 HW 30 DAS	0.1	3.8	12.9	8.8	4.1	95.45	203.43
Pendimethalin 1 + 1 HW 30 DAS	0.2	3.0	11.6	7.5	4.1	90.00	195.10
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DAS	0.2	3.1	11.7	7.6	4.1	190.90	92.84
Oxadiazon 1.0	0.3	3.1	12.7	8.7	4.0	40.90	238.91
Thiobencarb 1.5	1.4	3.0	10.8	7.0	3.8	29.81	208.88
Oxadiazon 0.75	0.9	3.1	11.6	7.9	3.7	31.81	195.85
Thiobencarb 1.5 + 2,4-D EE 1.0	1.8	2.8	10.3	6.8	3.6	40.27	165.65
Hand hoeing 20 and 40 DAS	2.5	2.7	10.0	6.6	3.5	50.90	137.60
Thiobencarb 2.0	1.2	2.5	10.5	7.4	3.1	39.45	104.97
Pendimethalin 2.0	2.3	2.4	8.6	5.2	3.0	48.63	60.18
Pendimethalin 1.0 + 2,4-D EE 1.0	1.6	2.2	9.4	6.5	2.9	35.90	74.87
Weedy check	3.4	2.0	7.4	5.3	2.2	—	—
Pendimethalin 1.0	3.1	2.2	7.1	5.2	1.9	26.36	-64.94
CD at 5%	0.853	0.76	3.117	2.22	1.286		

^aHerbicide measurements are in kg ai/ha. HW = hand weeding. EE = ethyl ester. ^bCost of herbicide and labor: thiobencarb = \$1 7.45/liter, pendimethalin (G) = \$21.81/kg, oxadiazon = \$36.36/liter, 2,4-D EE = \$9.54/kg, application charges = \$4.54/ha, Cost of hand weeding 1 = \$127.27/ha, cost of hand weeding 2 = \$63.63/ha, cost of hoeing 1 = \$31.81/ha, cost of hoeing 2 = \$19.09/ha, hand weeding after herbicide application = \$63.36/ha, price of rice = \$136.3/t, and price of straw = \$8.18/t. ^cProfit = grain yield + straw yield minus treatment cost.

Weed control in hybrid rice

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We evaluated some herbicides to control weeds in hybrid rice Shen Zhan 97A/Saddang in the 1985-86 wet season. Herbicides were applied 3 d after transplanting.

The herbicides did not influence tillering and plant height. MCPA-K salt, oxadiazon, thiobencarb, and 2,4-D were not significantly different in controlling broadleaves, grasses, and sedges (see table). Piperophos + 2,4-D was not significantly different from hand weeding, especially for controlling grasses. Highest yield was with hand

Effect of some herbicides on tillering, plant height, weeds, and grain yield in hybrid rice. Maros, Indonesia, 1985-86 wet season.

Treatment	kg ai/ha	Tillers (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Dry weed ^a (g/m ²)			Grain yield (t/ha)
				Broad-leaves	Grasses	Sedges	
MCPA K salt	0.40	12	70	2.8 bc	2.0 b	1.2 bc	3.3 c
Oxadiazon	0.50	10	60	3.4 c	2.4 b	1.5 cd	3.4 c
Piperophos + 2,4-D	0.33 + 0.17	13	71	1.5 b	1.1 a	0.9 b	4.2 b
Thiobencarb	1.00	12	67	3.5 c	2.3 b	1.0 bc	3.2 cd
2,4-D	0.85	12	66	3.1 c	2.8 b	1.3 cd	3.4 c
Hand weeding 7 and 35 DT ^b		12	70	0.6 a	0.4 a	0.0 a	5.2 a
Unweeded control		10	70	8.9 d	5.1 c	2.9 d	2.3 d
CV (%)		20	7	16.4	21.5	23.6	12.0

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Data transformed to log (x + 1). ^bDays after transplanting.

weeding, then with piperophos + 2,4-D. Thiobencarb increased yield 35%. □

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Pomacea snails in the Philippines

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Pomacea snails indigenous to South America were recently introduced for human food in Taiwan (China), Japan, and the Philippines. Scientific names,

frequently confused, were determined by Habe as follows:

Family: Pilidae (Ampullariidae)
Pomacea canaliculata (Lamarck)
Ampullaria canaliculata
Ampullarium insularum Hamada et Matsumoto 1985 (nec d'Orbigny 1839)

Ampullarius insularus Chang 1985 (nec d'Orbigny 1839)
Ampullarius insularus. Miyazaki 1985 (nec d'Orbigny 1839)
Ampullarius insularus Miyahara et al. 1986 (nec d'Orbigny 1839)
Pomacea gigas (Spix)
Ampullaria gigas